

The Alexander Decadrachms of Babylon

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This essay examines the impact of recent examples in commerce on our understanding of the Babylonian decadrachms bearing the image of the head Herakles (obverse) and Zeus enthroned (reverse) struck under Alexander the Great in 325-324 BC. The Babylonian decadrachms of Alexander the Great were first documented in the nineteenth century with two examples¹ from a hoard in commerce; the Babylon 1849 Hoard (*IGCH* 1749). Most of the decadrachms in this find were melted down. However, it is probable that at least two examples that entered the numismatic collections of the Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF) and the Athens Numismatic Museum in the nineteenth century originated from the same find; perhaps from the few examples from the find that were reputedly carried to India.² This small number of Alexander decadrachms remained unchanged for more than a century, until the Babylonian (Iraq) 1973 hoard in commerce (*CH* 1.38).³ This saw at least five examples enter numismatic trade. These were documented by Martin Price in 1991⁴ by which time he came to associate a further three examples in commerce with hoard. This brought to twelve the then known examples of the Babylon decadrachms in which Price⁵ identified three varieties based on mint controls and their placement (Price 3598, 3600 and 3618A). These paralleled the same mint controls on some of the early Babylon Group 2 tetradrachms. In subsequent years a few specimens appeared in auctions, but the paucity of surviving examples constrained further study of the emission, and here the understanding of the coinage rested for almost three decades.

Now the situation has changed. In the five years to 2019 a further 22 examples were identified for the first time in auctions, all without a verifiable provenance. This suggests the introduction of material from a new find into commerce. Most of the coins exhibit considerable surface corrosion, suggestive of protracted immersion, perhaps originating from a common source.⁶ This has tripled the corpus of known specimens, although unfortunately for our understanding all are absent a controlled find context. Yet this new material still offers much fragmentary evidence with which to evaluate the coinage. Like all the examples of the coinage that have come before, we are left to salvage from the pieces whatever information we can regarding their origin and significance. To this effect, presented below is a die study of this new material⁷ that builds on Price's record of the decadrachms in the Babylon 1973 commerce hoard. The catalogue of the Alexander decadrachms follows the discussion, accompanied by two plates of images that illustrate key aspects of the study.

¹ Vaux (1851): 70-74, BM 1850,0412.1; Friedländer (1881): 5, Münzkabinett Berlin 18202989.

² Leake (1856): 5 records that BM 1850,0412.1 'was procured by Major Rawlinson, on the site of Babylon, and was found, as he informs me, in the year 1849, together with many other decadrachms of Alexander in the ruins called the temple of Belus; the greater part were melted at Bagdad; a few more were carried to India. There can be little doubt they were struck at Babylon.'

³ Price (1975): 14-16.

⁴ Price (1991b): 163-65 and 69.

⁵ Price (1991a).

⁶ In 2019 The BBC World Service (News Arabic) produced a report identifying the possibility that many of these newly identified decadrachms in commerce may have originated from a find by fisherman dispersed on the seafloor, offshore of the township of Blakhiyah (ancient Anthedon) in the Gaza strip in 2017: 'The mystery of Alexander the Great's lost coins' <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JlPzGTDIU-8> (accessed June 2020).

⁷ Based on a survey of numismatic auctions to January 2021.

Table 1. Summary: Babylon decadrachm series.

Series	Price	Mint controls	Reverse iconographic detail
Series 1			
1.1	3598(?)	<TH> (if truly present) above the horizontal strut of the <i>diphros</i> . Zeus depicted in an archaized style identical to the Babylon Group 1.1 tetradrachms, legs disposed in parallel.	
Series 2			
2.1	3600	<TH> placed below the throne strut. Thick unadorned tabular footstool. Zeus's legs rigidly parallel.	
2.2	-	<LF> M <TH>	
Series 3 (transitional)			
3.1	-	None (?)	Horizontal strut discarded.
3.2	3598	<TH> , M	Zeus's legs rigidly parallel, then l. leg drawn back slightly. Thin footstool rests on a ground line.
Series 4			
4.1	-	<LF> Bee <TH> <EX> M	Throne with unbraced spindly legs.
4.2	3618A	<LF> Bee <TH> , M	Zeus depicted with his left leg drawn back strongly from the right.
4.3	3598	<TH> , M	Thin tabular footstool adorned by dots supported by two sigmoidal legs.

In this enlarged corpus of the decadrachms we can now recognise a developmental sequence consisting of four series defined primarily by a progression of reverse iconographic details summarized in Table 1, illustrated on Plates 1-2. In the four series eight different varieties are identified based on the varying placement of two mint marks; a monogram and a letter M, accompanied on some of Series 4 by a Bee symbol in the left field (Tables 1 and 2). Three of these are new varieties, in addition to the three types recognized by Price (Table 1). Five obverse dies are identified in the sequence (Figure 1). Three of these, A2, A3 and A4, were previously known.⁸ The varieties of Series 2-4 are obverse die linked in a compact sequence (Table 2). Only one reverse die link is identified; A4 is linked to A5 by P21 in Series 4.3. Reverse dies outnumber obverse dies 5.2:1 reflecting the high breakage rate of large diameter reverse dies under the very heavy hammer blows required to impart the design on large diameter metal flans.

⁸ Waggoner (1968): 33, nos. 19-21.

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Figure 1. Decadrachm obverse dies.

Table 2. Distribution of obverse dies.

Series	Mint controls	Obverse dies
1.1	<TH> (?), M	A1
2.1	<TH> <EX> M	A2, A3
2.2	<LF> M <TH>	A2
3.1	None (?)	A3
3.2	<TH> , M	A4
4.1	<LF> Bee <TH> <EX> M	A4
4.2	<LF> Bee <TH> , M	A4, A5
4.3	<TH> , M	A4, A5

The statistical coverage (*Cest*)⁹ of 0.97 for the obverse dies indicates that the catalogue presents a meaningful sample of the mintage (Table 3). It is estimated that 6 ± 1 obverse dies were commissioned for the mintage (Table 3).¹⁰ Thus, the emission was of modest size. Assuming a decadrachm obverse die productivity of 5,000-10,000 coins; one quarter to one half that considered likely for a smaller diameter tetradrachm die, then six obverse dies might have struck approximately 30,000-60,000 decadrachms, the struck equivalent of 50-100 Attic talents of silver.

Table 3. Obverse die statistics.

Sample size (<i>n</i>)	36
Obverse dies (<i>d</i>)	5
Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	1
Characteristic Index (<i>n/d</i>)	7.2
Coverage (<i>Cest</i>)	0.97
Estimated dies (<i>Dest</i>)	5.8
95% Confidence interval	4.8-7.0

Turning now to the question of how the decadrachms fit within the Babylonian mintage and coinage system. It has long been understood that the decadrachms were an early component of the Babylon Group 2 emission, which consisted primarily of tetradrachms.¹¹ We can now clarify this further by reference to stylistic affinities and developments apparent in the expanded corpus of the coinage, which establish that the decadrachms were but an extension of the iconographic progression evidenced in the earliest Babylon Group 1 tetradrachms.¹² With the exception of die A4, the decadrachm obverse dies are of a uniform style, a continuation of that observed in the tetradrachm obverse dies of Group 1.1 (Plate 1, A¹³). This style also to be found on some the earliest Group 2 tetradrachms.¹⁴ One of its characteristics is an idealized, tightly structured depiction of the tufts of hair in the mane of the lion scalp headdress. In the Babylon mintage A4 marks the first departure from this, replacing the tightly structured tufts with more realistically depicted, loosely tangled tufts in the mane. The loosely tangled mane on A4 is an artistic advance in realism over that found on the balance of the obverse dies.

The reverse style of the sole known example of Series 1 (Plate 1, 1) is very telling of a close association with Group 1.1, for it is identically styled to the tetradrachms of the latter (Plate 1, A). Both display a distinctively styled Zeus seated on a *diphros* with no footstool beneath his feet. This style has its origin in the depiction of Baaltars found on some examples of the Babylonian lion staters of Mazaios, dated 3-5 years before the start of the Babylonian Alexandrine coinage.¹⁵ Its presence on the Series 1 decadrachm is atypical of the following series on which Zeus is seated on a

⁹ Esty 2006: 357, formula 1.

¹⁰ Esty (2011): 43-58.

¹¹ Price (1991a); Waggoner (1968).

¹² Taylor (2018).

¹³ Taylor (2018): Group 1.1, no. 7 (this coin); LWHT Coll. 145.

¹⁴ Taylor (2018): 21-24.

¹⁵ Taylor (2018):19-20.

high-backed throne, his feet resting on a footstool. This sets Series 1 apart, the earliest example of the decadrachms to be struck. Also differing from subsequent series, the mint controls are equally disposed above and below the horizontal strut bracing the legs of the *diphros*, whereas the primary mint mark, the monogram, which is found on the balance of the decadrachms. Within the interpretational uncertainty, it could equally well be the letter Φ , which with M mint mark is characteristic of Babylon Group 1. Should a new example come to light to confirm this possibility, then we would have evidence that the initial striking of the decadrachms coincided with the start of the Group 1.1 tetradrachm mintage, an intriguing possibility. For the present, all we can say is that the iconographic style and detail of the reverse indicates a close chronological association between the Series 1 decadrachm and the Group 1.1 tetradrachms.

Series 2 (Plate 1, 3-9) presents a familiar, more evolved reverse iconography (Table 1). Zeus is portrayed seated on a high-backed throne rather than a *diphros*. The throne legs are braced by a single horizontal strut. Zeus's legs are disposed rigidly side by side, in parallel, while his feet rest on a thick, tabular footstool (Figure 2a).

Figure 2. Footstool and throne legs: progression in iconography.

A notable development in Series 2 is the appearance of two eagles perched on the throne back either side of Zeus's shoulders (Figure 3). This previously undocumented phenomenon is present on five of the seven reverse dies. It is only found on Series 2. It has the appearance of a brief period of iconographic experimentation, subsequently abandoned. Unlike Series 1, the mint marks are no longer constrained to the space beneath the throne, although the primary mark is always found between the throne legs, below the horizontal strut. The M mint mark appears either in the exergue (Series 2.1), or in the left field (series 2.2). In this it appears that we are witness to a tension in finding the appropriate placement for the second of the two mint controls, with the space beneath the throne constrained by the presence of the horizontal strut.

Figure 3. Eagles perched on throne back.

Series 3 (Plate 2, 13-15) sees this tension addressed with the removal of the horizontal strut allowing for easy placement of the two mint controls between the legs of the throne (Series 3.2). Consequently, an enlarged monogram is uppermost, although on one example mint controls may be absent (Series 3.1), a point impossible to establish with confidence due to smoothing and tooling of the coin in question. Associated with this development, the thick foot stool beneath Zeus's feet is displaced by a thin irregular form, resting on a ground line in the case of die P10 (Figure 2b), this being the only occurrence of the ground line in the sequence. In the course of Series 3 the rigid parallel legs depiction of Zeus is abandoned. His right leg below the knee is advanced somewhat, while the left leg (that closest the viewer) is drawn back ever so slightly from the right (Plate 2, 14-15). This results in a less rigid depiction. These changes presage the final form of the reverse on Series 4, yet enthroned Zeus maintains many of the stylistic attributes of Series 2. In this respect Series 3 is transitional between Series 2 and Series 4. It also coincides with the introduction of the distinctively styled obverse die A4 into the decadrachm emission. With its more realistic depiction of the mane on the lion skin headdress, A4 suggests the introduction of at least one new engraver into the workplace, a point reinforced by the markedly different style of the reverse dies of Series 4 with which it is paired. Die A4 links Series 3 to Series 4, where on type 4.3 it is observed in a more advanced state of wear, confirming the relative sequencing of the two series.

Series 4 (Plate 2, 16-31) marks the final evolution of the decadrachm reverse iconography. Gone is the rigid parallel legs depiction of Zeus, replaced by a more fluid portrayal in which the left leg of Zeus is drawn tightly back towards the leading foot of the throne so that the legs below the knee define an inverted V, or Λ (*lambda*) shape. The *lambda* legs depiction is also found on the contemporaneous Babylon Group 2 tetradrachms. Additionally, the legs of the Series 4 throne are now defined in a tall, slender, relatively unadorned and unbraced form compared to the squat, heavily turned legs found on Series 2 and 3. Similarly, the footstool is presented as a slender delicate tabular form resting on small sigmoidal legs, the side of the stool often adorned by beading (Figure 2c); far lighter and more elaborate than the depiction of Series 2 and 3. The overall iconography of the Series 4 reverse dies is that of a lighter, fluid presentation compared to that found in the preceding series; clearly one that is more artistically evolved than the earlier sequence. Together with the evolved style of obverse die A4, this establishes the relative chronological order in of Series 4 in the decadrachm sequence as well as its relationship to the similarly styled early Group 2 tetradrachms (Table 4).

A notable development in Series 4 is the appearance of the Bee symbol in the left field of Series 4.1 and 4.2, also found on the Group 2 tetradrachms. Symbols were introduced in the last stage of the Group 1 emission, probably to distinguish the output from different striking teams in a multi-anvil parallel striking (Table 4).¹⁶ On their introduction they were placed in the exergue, further adding to the difficulty in seeking to place all mint controls in the confined space beneath the throne. The symbols were then moved to the left field early in the Group 2 mintage.¹⁷ The Bee symbol in the left field of Series 4.1-4.2 serves to date the late Series 3 and early Series 4 to the time when this left field symbol placement was adopted in the Group 2 tetradrachms (Table 4). The interwoven use of dies A4 and A5 throughout Series 4 (Table 2), suggests that these two dies may have been used in parallel, on two anvils. However, the sample of the coinage is insufficient to fully demonstrate this aspect.

¹⁶ Taylor (2018).

¹⁷ Taylor (2018): 21-23.

Table 4 . Babylon Groups 1 and 2: relative chronology.

BC	Decadrachms	Tetradrachms		
326/5	M Series 1 (A1) Series 2 (A2, A3) Series 3 (A3, A4) Series 4 (A4, A5)	Group 1.1	Group 1.2	Group 1.2
		Φ M	Φ M	
		A1-A4	A5-A11	
		Group 2		
325/4		M		Φ M
		6 A dies		6 Symbols
				A10-A11
			Group 2	
			M	
			33 Symbols	
			77 A dies	

Conclusions

The newly identified examples of the Alexander decadrachm when combined with the dozen previously known examples provide improved insight into the production of the coinage, which commenced in the earliest period of Alexander’s Babylonian coinage in 325 BC.¹⁸ Potentially, decadrachm Series 1 was struck in parallel with the last of the Group 1.1 coinage. If not, it immediately followed on from the latter (Table 4). Following this, the iconography and mint control conventions of decadrachm coinage continued to develop along the path established in the Group 1 tetradrachms, in parallel with the same trends in the earliest of the Group 2 tetradrachms. Occurring within the productive life of five obverse dies, in a compact die sequence, these developments are likely to have occurred over a period of months rather than years, but are sufficient to define four series in a continuum of artistic evolution that preceded the adoption of the crossed legs depiction of Zeus, which was to characterize the Group 3 and subsequent Babylon tetradrachm emissions. The observed pattern of development is consistent with the recently proposed model of the mint’s operation in the transition from the Group 1 to Group 2 tetradrachm sequence (Table 4).¹⁹

With a larger sample of the decadrachm coinage, we are now in a position to quantify the magnitude of the emission, which is statistically estimated to have been struck from six obverse dies, five of which are observed in the current corpus of the coinage. This was a small, time limited mintage, probably struck in anticipation of a special occasion, rather than forming a regular component of Alexander’s monetary system. Based on the chronology inferred from the iconographic progression across the four series and their relative relationship to the tetradrachms of Groups 1 and 2, the decadrachms were struck preparatory to the return of Alexander the Great to Babylon at the conclusion of his eastern anabasis. Preparations for the great marriage celebration

¹⁸ Taylor (2018) for the chronological evidence.

¹⁹ Taylor 2018): 21-24 and table 5.

at nearby Susa, 350 km east of Babylon, in the Spring of 324 BC may have motivated their mintage.²⁰ Alternatively, the anticipated, but subsequently delayed, entry of Alexander to Babylon may have been the reason for the striking of this denomination.

Martin Price in closing his exposition of the Alexander decadrachms that originated from the Babylon 1973 commerce hoard stated that 'It is salutary to remember how much of our knowledge of ancient coinage relies on the chance survival of the coins. Inevitably, there is much to be learned in the future.'²¹ This still remains the case, even with an enlarged corpus of the Alexander decadrachms struck at Babylon.

CATALOGUE

Series 1

Obv.: Head of Herakles r. wearing lionskin headdress, dotted border.

Rev: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus holding sceptre and eagle, seated l. on a *diphros* braced by a single horizontal strut, dotted border.

1.1	Price 3598 var.	<TH>		(?), M	
	dies	g	axes		
1.*	A1-P1	36.39	12	Numismatik Naumann 65 (2018), 76. Heavily corroded but of an identical reverse style to Babylon Group 1.1, the earliest Alexander issue from the mint.	

Series 2

Obv.: Head of Herakles r. wearing lionskin headdress, dotted border.

Rev: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus holding sceptre and eagle, seated l. on a high-backed throne braced by a single horizontal strut, dotted border. Two eagles perched on throne back on some examples.

2.1	Price 3600	<TH>		<EX>	M.
2.	A2-P2	41.96	9	Bertolami Fine Arts 8 (2014), 196; Spink and Son inventory. P2 - two eagles perched on throne back.	
3.*	A2-P2	30.09	5	Roma Numismatics XV (2018), 120.	

²⁰ Taylor (2019): Susa did not possess a mint at this time; it opened c. 319/8 BC.

²¹ Price (1991b): 65.

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4.	A2-P3	40.66		Price <i>Circulation</i> , 6; Numismatica Ars Classica NAC AG 72 (2013), 344; Price pl. CLIX 3600 (this coin); CH 1 (1975), fig. 6.2; Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38. P3 - two eagles perched on throne back.
5.	A2 -P4	36.87	12	Heritage 3064 (2019), 30046. P4 - two eagles perched on throne back. Very corroded coin.
6.	A2-P?	28.61	5	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 54 (2019), 133. Reverse details lost to coin wear.
7.*	A3-P5	40.35	4	Roma Numismatics XVII (2019), 397.
8.	A3-P6	36.58	6	Heritage 3076 (2019), 30047. Very corroded coin.
2.2	Price -			<LF> M; <TH>
9.*	A2-P7	40.38	3	Roma Numismatics XIV (2017), 111. P7 - two eagles perched on throne back.
10.	A2-P8	42.55	2	Triton XXIV (2021), lot 467; Leu 54 (1992), 86. P8 - two eagles perched on throne back.
11.	A2-P8?	34.78	10	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (2018), 117. Worn coin - fine detail on the reverse is lost including legend and mint marks.
12.	A2?-P?	-	-	Waggoner (1968), 20a is an example of Price 3598. The available coin image does not permit die identification, although A2 is likely.

Series 3 (transitional)

Obv.: Head of Herakles r. wearing lionskin headdress, dotted border.

Rev: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus holding sceptre and eagle, seated l. on a high-backed throne (no bracing strut), dotted border.

3.1	Price -			No mint marks (?) - removed by smoothing/tooling?
13.*	A3-P9	41.65	9	Münzkabinett Berlin 18202989; Babylon 1849 Hoard IGCH 1749. No trace of mint marks in the smoothed areas beneath the throne and left field.
3.2	Price 3598			<TH> , M
14.*	A4-P10	41.62	8	Roma Numismatics XVI (2018), 221. P10 - footstool rests on a ground line.
15.*	A4-P10	40.86	6	BM 1850,0412.1; Le Rider (2007), pl. 8, 3; Babylon 1849 Hoard IGCH 1749.

Series 4

Obv.: Head of Herakles r. wearing lionskin headdress, dotted border.

Rev: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus holding sceptre and eagle, seated l. on a high-backed throne (no bracing strut), dotted border. Zeus's left leg strongly drawn back from the right.

4.1	Price -			<LF> Bee <TH> <EX> M
16.*	A4-P11	41.43	n.r.	Goldberg 116 (2020), 809; The New York Sale 48 (2019), 5.
4.2	Price 3618A			<LF> Bee <TH> , M
17.	A4-P12	42.28	12	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 8; The New York Sale 27 (2012), 307; Spink 71 (1989), 49. Believed to be ex Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38.
18.	A4-P12	42.99	n.r.	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 7, pl.15, 7; 1989 commerce. Believed to be ex Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38.
19.*	A5-P13	40.15	4	Roma Numismatics XIV (2017), 112.
20.	A5-P14	39.61	10	Heritage 3081 (2020), 32009; Heritage 3061 (2019), 32022.
21.	A?-P14	31.51	10	CNG eAuction 410 (2017), 16. Worn and corroded coin - die identity uncertain.
4.3	Price 3598			<TH> , M
22.	A4-P15	n.r.	n.r.	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 5; CH 1 (1975), fig. 6.1; Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38.
23.	A4-P16	42.24	4	BnF FRBNF41836176.
24.	A4-P17	n.r.	n.r.	Waggoner (1968), 19b; Athens Numismatic Museum.
25.	A4-P18	41.04	8	Goldberg 112 (2019), 1503.
26.	A4-P19	40.63	12	CNG eAuction 412 (2018), 84.
27.	A4-P20	36.63	5	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 54 (2019), 132.
28.	A4-P20	41.76	n.r.	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 4; Sotheby's (1990 Hunt Coll.), 102; Bank Leu 13 (1975), 129; Mørkholm (1991), pl. II, 30; Mitchiner (1975): 11, Type 1(b). A4 well worn.
29.*	A4-P21	41.22	1	Heritage 3048 (2016), 32024; Heritage 3044 (2016), 31020. A4 die break obliterates ear of lion scalp - die in most worn state.
30.	A5-P21	41.09	10	Roma Numismatics XV (2018), 121. A5 well worn. Off-centre strike leaves M mint mark off-flan.
31.*	A5-P22	41.76	5	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 1; ANS 1974.274.1; Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38.
32.	A5-P23	39.70	1	Nomos Obolos web auction 1 (2018), 62; Hess Divo 333 (2017), 26.

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33.	A5-P24	41.47	9	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 2; Fritz Rudolf Künker GmbH & Co. KG 280 (2016), 163; Price 3598 Pl. CLIX, 3598; CH 1 (1975), fig. 6.3; Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38.
34.	A5-P25	38.47	n.r.	Numismatica Ars Classica NAC AG 84 (2015), 600.
35.	A5-P26	41.51	4	Künker 318 (2019), 604; Münzen und Medaillen 64 (1984), 97.
36.	A5-P?	43.23	n.r.	Price <i>Circulation</i> , 3; 1989 commerce. Believed to be ex Babylon 1973 Hoard CH 1.38. Obverse die identification and details from Price.

Too worn for die and type identification

37.	-	23.27	1	Roma Numismatics E-sale 54 (2019), 134; Roma E-Sale 43 (2018), 103.
38.	-	26.66	11	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 42 (2018), 122.

Postscript

Shortly before going to press, a 2019 paper by Bauzou and Thevenin titled ‘Un trésor considérable et perdu: le trésor d’Alexandres de Gaza’ was brought to my attention. It documents the few known facts of the offshore Gaza find which the authors associate with the discovery of a 5th century Greek bronze statue by fishermen in the shallow nearshore waters off the Gaza Strip, opposite the ancient site of Blakhiyah-Anthédon. Coins scattered on the seabed were progressively recovered by fishermen in the period 2013-2017, the better specimens disbursed into international numismatic trade, the poor condition material melted down. From sources in Gaza, the authors record five additional decadrachms that did not find their way into numismatic trade. Images of these coins, Bauzou and Thevenin pl. 3, 32-36, establish that they were struck respectively from dies A5, A2, A3, A4, and A5(?). From these and other examples in recent commerce, they identified four obverse decadrachm dies in the sequence.²² However, the authors do not consider the progression in the development of the reverse iconography and its significance for the interpretation of the striking sequence.

²² Bauzou and Thevenin consider the sole example from die A1 to be have been struck from A4. Despite the heavy corrosion of the former, it is ascertained that the original outlines of the chin, neck truncation and knot of the lionskin do not conform to the outlines of the same elements on A4. The differences are unlikely to be the result of corrosion alone. The reverse die to which A1 is paired is unequivocally of the earliest style, while those paired to A4 are of a of a demonstrably later style, the last in the sequence, reinforcing the interpretation that A1 and A4 are in fact different dies.

Plate 1

Babylon Group 1
1.1 Tetradrachm

A

Babylon Group 2
Decadrachm Series 1

1

Series 2

3

7

9

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Plate 2

Series 3 (transitional)

13

14

15

Series 4

16

19

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31

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